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A Proactive Approach to the Recovery and Recycling of Photovoltaic Modules

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D1.2 Waste PV source secured

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
EoL	End of Life
PV	Photovoltaic
FhG	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft
EVA	Ethylene vinyl acetate

1. Executive summary

- Delivery of EoL-PV-Modules through the associated Partner has begun.
- 40 Modules and 500 kg of shredded are at hand at the CSP for investigations.
- Further quantities will be supplied upon request.
- Modules from Kalyon PV will be delivered soon.

The delivery D1.2 is concerned with securing a sufficient number of PV modules and a sufficiently large quantity of PV waste to ensure the planned investigations in the project. In this report we present the fulfilment of this task in time.

2. Planned criteria

A report on the PV module waste delivered will be prepared, which will include essential module parameters. This overview is essential for the further progress of the work within WP2.

3. Waste PV source

At the start of the project the resources for the recycling need to be secured. Therefore, different types of waste PV sources are collected at the FhG CSP. Most of the material will come from the associated partner Reiling GmbH in Germany. They will provide us on request up to 60 t of complete or shredded modules for further treatment in the project.

Until now we already have received complete PV-modules (Figure 1 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**) as well as shredded material (Figure 2). At the moment we have 40 intact PV-modules and 500 kg of shredded modules at hand at Fraunhofer CSP for the start of the planned investigations according to the project plan. Also, the project partner Kalyon PV will supply modules from their production to further investigate their recyclability.

FIGURE 1: PART OF THE PV-MODULES FOR RECYCLING INVESTIGATIONS

FIGURE 2: SHREDDED PV-MODULES FOR RECYCLING ACTIVITIES

The data of the PV-modules are collected in a database. An example of these data is given in Figure 3. Data collected is divided into general data (producer, module type, serial number, weight, dimension), cell data (dimension, type, number of busbars, number of silver contacts), glass data (thickness, structure, Sb-content) and polymer data (used back sheet, EVA). These parameters are listed in Table 1. The parameter list will be expanded or reduced according to the needs in the project.

Nr.	Producer	Module type	S/N	Year of production	Pmax / W	weight / kg	dimension / mm			Measured weight / kg	frame connection	PV laminate weight / kg	Al-frame weight (measured) / kg	Frame condition	Full frame weight (calculated) / kg	J.Box+Connectors weight (measured) / kg	cable (measured) / kg	cell number	mono/poly	cell geometry	Zelle			
							L	W	H												cell dimensions / mm	wafer thickness / μm	Si / kg	
A1	bp solar	BP71755	S20406303209349	2004	175	15,4	1593	790	50									6	12	mono	semi	125	125	2
A2	bp solar	BP71855 BP 7185	S20604285081878	2006	185	15,4	1593	790	50	screw								6	12	mono	semi	125	125	2
A3	bp solar	BP4175N	O40810258064502	2008	175	15,4	1593	790	50	14,20 screw		2,553						6	12	mono	semi	125	125	2
A4	suntaics	STC 165-35MS-E	SF1600512G111		165					15,48 glue		2,954						6	12	mono	semi	125	125	2
A5	Eging PV	EGM-180	S2230407375	2010	180	15,5	1580	808	50	glue								6	12	mono	semi	125	125	2
A6	Eging PV	EGM-180	S1130407209	2010	180	15,5	1580	808	50	glue								6	12	mono	semi	125	125	2
A7	Eging PV	EGM-180	S2230407380	2010	180	15,5	1580	808	50	glue								6	12	mono	semi	125	125	2
A8	Eging PV	EGM-180	S4124405979	2010	180	15,5	1580	808	50	glue								6	12	mono	semi	125	125	2
A9	CEEG Solar	SST245*60M	SST3110903153		245	20	1640	990	50	19,52 glue		3,783						6	10	mono	semi	156	156	3
A10	Solarfun	SF220-30-1P240 SF 220-30-P	SF2204P1002BWO565	2008	240	22	1652	1000	50	20,77 glue		4,420						6	10	poly	full	156	156	3
A11	LDK Solar International Comp	LDK-220P-20	S10PM10540100465	2009	220	20	1642	994	40	19,16 glue		2,926						6	10	poly	full	156	156	2
A12	Conergy	Conergy PowerPlus 215P	0000988322 100412	2009	215	22	1651	986	46	23,00 screw		3,791						6	10	poly	full	156	156	3
A13	CSP ???		1316001							22,71 glue		3,135						6	10	poly	full	156	156	3
A14	CanadianSolar	CS6P-245P	A412070011659	2010	245	19	1638	982	40	screw								6	10	poly	full	156	156	3
A15	Tauber Solar	TSM60-156M	Z951112710902		240		1652	994	45	19,59 glue		3,373						6	10	mono	semi	156	156	3
A16	CanadianSolar	CS6P-245P	A812070010011	2010	245	19	1638	982	40	screw								6	10	poly	full	156	156	3
A17	Jetion Solar	JT230PCe	Pc0199801211	2013	230	22,5	1655	992	40	19,40 screw		3,006						6	10	poly	full	156	156	3
A18	REC	REC240PE	S000821052	2011	240	18	1665	991	38	glue								6	10	poly	full	156	156	3
A19	REC	REC240PE	S000848931	2011	240	18	1665	991	38	glue								6	10	poly	full	156	156	3
A20	Jinko Solar	JKM220P-60	4,52101E+19	2010	220	19	1650	992	45	19,07 screw		3,118						6	10	poly	full	156	156	2
A21	CanadianSolar	CS6P-240P	4,1143E+11	2010	240	19	1638	982	40	18,71 screw		3,148						6	10	poly	full	156	156	3

FIGURE 3: COLLECTED DATA FROM PV-MODULES

TABLE 1: PARAMETER LIST FOR THE PV-MODULE COLLECTION

Parameter	Unit	
module	producer	
	module type	
	serial number	
	year of production	
	power output (Pmax)	W
	weight (datasheet)	kg
	dimension (length*width*height)	mm
	weight (measured)	kg
	weight of PV laminate (without frame and junction box)	kg
frame	frame connection	glued or screwed
	weight of frame	kg
	frame condition	missing parts
Junction box	Junction box and connectors	kg
	cable	kg
cell	cell number (row*column)	
	cell crystallinity	mono or poly
	cell geometry	full or half; semi/pseudo
	cell dimensions (length*width)	mm
	wafer thickness	μm
	weight of Si	kg
	number of busbars	
	number of Ag contacts	
width of Ag contacts	μm	

glass	weight of Ag	g
	glass thickness	mm
	weight of glass	kg
	Sb content	wt. %
polymers	polymer of backsheet	
	thickness of backsheet	µm
	weight of backsheet	kg
	fluorine content	yes or no
	surface structure	rough or smooth
	thickness of EVA	µm
	weight of EVA	kg

4. Conclusion

The waste PV stream for the project is secured. Different materials can be delivered upon request by the associated partner Reiling GmbH and our project partner Kalyon PV.

